

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF DEVELOPING READING COMPETENCES IN FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Teachers should make students understand that the process of reading literary works gives a great sense of satisfaction. In addition, as a result of the teacher telling his future English language teachers what is thought about in the selected work, they can arouse interest in this work. The article describes methods of developing reading competencies in future English language teachers.*

Keywords: *reading literary works, developing reading competencies.*

INTRODUCTION

The role of pedagogues in the formation of interest in the examples of fiction in future elementary English language teachers is incomparable, they are familiar with Uzbek folklore, examples of children's literature and recommend for extracurricular pedagogical processes and independent study at home by choosing examples of fiction that are interesting for future English language teachers. It is desirable for students to organize regular, group and individual interviews, discussions and debates about the artistic works they read.

Future English language teachers who are closely acquainted with examples of literary work develop memory and focus on one point. In addition, future English language teachers will develop figurative thinking and literacy. They will understand the main idea of a work of art and the skills of speaking. As a result, they develop analytical thinking effectively. If they are regularly engaged in reading examples of fiction, their outlook, intellect, cognitive activity will develop, and positive moral qualities will be formed.

In the image of the heroes of the play, they learn the experience of careful attitude towards the environment, understand the subtleties of interpersonal relationships. After entering school, students need to learn more information every day. Therefore, teachers should gradually increase the time spent on reading minutes, cooperate closely with parents in this area, and recommend literary works for future English teachers to read according to their age.

DISCUSSIONS

Future English teachers are especially interested in reading fairy tales related to the plot of cartoons: "Emerald and Precious", "Proud Rabbit", "The Wolf and the Goat". Books Future English teaches teachers to think and feel the experiences of fairy-tale characters.

Although children can read a particular fairy tale or story on their own, teachers and parents should not stop encouraging them to read. As a result of expressive reading, words are combined with images. By explaining the unfamiliar words and phrases in the text, the teacher helps future English teachers to easily understand the content of the work.

7-9-year-old children cannot focus on certain events for a long time. Their eyes get tired quickly. As a result, some words and phrases may be incomprehensible. Because of this, they do not understand the text and are completely bored with reading.

For 7-8-year-old children, teachers and parents should read the works continuously. They should choose a comfortable place to read. This will interest the children and make them wonder what will happen next. Children should not just read the work. Its topic should be a reason for discussion among classmates. It is important for children to be able to put themselves in the place of the hero of the work and master the methods of finding solutions to the difficulties faced by this hero.

Children should be encouraged to read works decorated with quality pictures and illustrations. Knowing the name of the artist who decorated such books is useful for future English teachers. Future English language teachers should be given tasks about drawing pictures based on the work, drawing pictures of the heroes of the work of art.

It is advisable for primary school teachers to visit libraries with children often, to familiarize them with various editions of children's literature samples. Children should be familiar with works of art as well as with various dictionaries. It is also helpful for teachers to advise parents to purchase educational works of art and children's encyclopedias for their children.

The following types of work can be used to form interest in examples of fiction in primary school children. Reading works of art in the classroom, reading during educational activities outside the classroom, establishing cooperation with the school librarian in order to form children's reading skills, working with parents to form children's interest in examples of fiction.

In the course of the research, a model of pedagogical process was developed, aimed at forming interest in literary examples of future English language teachers through reading. This model consists of components such as motivational-targeted, didactic approaches, technological processes and evaluation.

One of the main tasks of today is the process of directing the future English language teachers to form interest in the examples of fiction, as well as to form the knowledge, skills, skills and basic competencies necessary for them in the future. Non-standard lessons of an innovative character are of particular importance in the formation of interest in the examples of fiction for future English language teachers. These lessons include story-based lessons, travel lessons, auction lessons, dramatized lessons, quiz lessons, game lessons.

The types of work organized on the basis of the text of the work will develop expressive reading skills in future English language teachers in addition to forming an interest in examples of fiction. For example, dramatizing the text of the work or its specific part, reading based on forming a chain of sentences, reading in paragraphs, reading to find the part of the work that matches the picture, reading selectively the part of the work that helps to answer the questions.

Attention is paid to performing tasks that do not produce uniform results in the formation of interest in the art work being studied in future English language teachers. Unlike traditional questions, tests, exercises, they are focused on finding possible answers. These responses are unique and provide an opportunity for future English teachers to express themselves creatively.

Literary games and literary evenings play an important role in developing interest in literary works in future English language teachers. Artistic games can be organized as follows:

- Games and exercises aimed at developing speech in future English language teachers;
- artistic puzzles;
- art quizzes;
- games based on a certain style.

Various activities are organized in cooperation with cultural institutions: library hours, trips to museums, participation in exhibitions, participation in readers' contests, staging fairy tales, etc. Based on the orientation of the reading lessons first of all to the personality of future English language teachers, the possibilities of forming interest in the samples of artistic works will be expanded. On this basis, pedagogical tools, methods and methods serving this purpose are presented. They are:

1) Method of personal experience activation. In this, the teacher offers prospective English teachers to enter the situation of the characters of the play. In this process, Prospective English teachers choose specific situations related to their personal lives. Prospective English teachers are tasked with writing about their feelings and experiences and comparing them with those of their classmates.

2) introspective analysis method - is a unique method of teaching works of art to future English language teachers. Certain situations are always described in works of art. These situations are related to human life. It expresses human experiences and penetrates into the hearts of future English language teachers. One of the teacher's tasks is to challenge prospective English teachers to express their personal experiences.

3) Person-oriented theatrical method. This method is to interest future English language teachers in theatrical art work. In this place, it is thought about the use of the elements of dramatization of the artistic work in the formation of interest in the art work in the future English language teachers, in awakening their emotions. With the help of this method, future English language teachers feel the feelings and experiences of the protagonist of the work of art.

4) Method of self-creative expression. With the help of this method, future English language teachers imagine their place in the world of culture. For this purpose, the teacher should prepare future English language teachers for appropriate participation in various contests and stage performances.

In addition, it is appropriate for teachers to use various interactive technologies in reading and education lessons to interest future English language teachers in primary school. Teachers must install Mimio Studios on interactive whiteboards. Various art games can be placed and presented in it. Such technologies increase the effectiveness of reading lessons and develop the interest of future English language teachers in the works of fiction.

It should be noted that today there are many interactive technologies that serve to form the interest of future English language teachers in relation to examples of fiction. Teachers have the opportunity to develop the artistic taste, creative activity, speech, intelligence and logical, imaginative thinking of future English language teachers by using them effectively in reading lessons.

The use of the following set of methods is of particular importance in ensuring the successful solution of the tasks related to the formation of interest in the examples of fiction in future English language teachers.

In school practice, the following forms of work can be used to interest future English language teachers in examples of artistic works in reading lessons and extracurricular processes:

Debate refers to a discussion of specific issues among a group of prospective English teachers in relation to a work of art that has been read. It serves to form a general opinion about the work of art in future English language teachers. Discussion cannot be confused with discussion. Finding the right solution is the basis of any dispute. Does not represent a general judgment.

Methods of organization of the pedagogical process related to the formation of the interest of future elementary English language teachers in the examples of fiction	Methods of directing the interest of future elementary English teachers to fiction
Learning Exercise Demonstration Imitation Debate Conversation Game	Evaluation Peer evaluation praise Encouragement Competition

Conversation is the main form of organizing extracurricular activities. In this process, the teacher receives oral information about the artwork from the prospective English teachers. In doing so, it guides prospective English teachers in communicating about a specific topic of fiction. Conversation is one of the main methods and methods of teaching and upbringing. Conversation can be carried out in various forms: preparatory, informative, heuristic, restorative, repeating, summarizing, etc. Such types of work can be organized during study lessons and study hours outside the classroom.

Readers' competition is a way of working on a work of art. In this process, prospective English teachers present a work of their interest. Jury members will determine the winner.

Crossword is a form of self-examination, determination of knowledge.

A quiz is a pedagogical process consisting of answering questions based on a specific work.

Theatrical festival is also of particular importance in forming interest in the examples of fiction in future English language teachers. This goal-oriented process consists of several stages: selection of the repertoire, study of the author's creative activity, familiarization with the stage history of the work, selection of performers.

During reading hours, prospective English teachers and teachers bring non-curricular works of art to school. They are given a certain time. Each future English language teacher will independently read a work of art that interests him/her in a quiet, comfortable environment.

The following types of work can be used to arouse the interest of future English language teachers in the examples of artistic works based on the cooperation of primary school teachers with cultural institutions:

Library hours - where prospective English teachers work independently on a problem set before them. In this process, future English language teachers will work with examples of works of art, dictionaries, encyclopedias and independently familiarize themselves with library activities.
 Excursion to the museum - this involves the participation of future teachers of English in exhibitions of specific works and works of art.

Art Rooms – Incorporates out-of-classroom pedagogic activities aimed at developing an interest in art samples in future English language teachers. The following forms of creative activity are carried out in them:

creative: independent writing of scenarios for literary holidays, parties; work in creative groups;

play: participation in theater performances, independent work on one's role;

information: collecting information about the writer, his life and work, analyzing it and summarizing the evidence.

Every meeting in the art rooms involves a theatrical performance and an audience. The activity there is a flexible type of work based on independent communication on examples of fiction. This dialogue will take place between prospective English teachers and invited writers, poets and artists.

Readers' selection consists of a selection of theatrical plays.

Their regular attendance at the library is of particular importance in the formation of interest in works of art among future English language teachers. During the interviews, future English language teachers are introduced to new examples of children's literature. Practical classes on book selection will be held. The use of information technology serves to form a special interest in books by introducing future English language teachers to mass media. By exposing future English teachers to examples of fiction, a special love for books will be instilled in them.

It is proposed to use a number of effective methods for formation and development of reading skills in primary school students in foreign experiences. The didactic possibilities of some of these methods are discussed below:

Cassil's method. According to him, the teacher or parents stop reading the book at the most interesting part of the work. They say they don't have time to continue their studies at this point, they have other important things to do. In the end, the child wants to know how the life of the hero of the work was and takes the book in his hands. In elementary grades, children who are familiar with the letters of the alphabet try to read the rest of the work by themselves, although they are hesitant. But children who are not yet able to read well are forced to ask for help from other family members or the teacher at school. Then the answer of the family members or the teacher should be as follows: "Okay, I will help, but let's do it this way: I read two paragraphs, you read one!" The children, who are very interested in the development of the event, agree to this proposal.

"Ancient peoples" method. It is also called "People of books" (or "People of books" method). According to the essence of the method, the child was not only allowed to read a few lines or even half a page of an interesting work as a reward if he behaved in an exemplary manner, but also prepared cookies with the appearance of a book. The boy received such cookies in honor of the happy event of reading a book, because, in ancient times people accepted reading books as joy and celebration. The child had to remember this every time he picked up a book. If the child does not behave in an exemplary manner, then he is not allowed to read the book. This method is based on when children start reading the book.

Most researchers emphasize the advantage of the "Short-term" study method. The advantage of the method is that it is recommended to parents to read with the student for 10 minutes every day before bedtime without tiring him. If this method is followed, the students of the 1st-2nd grade of the primary school will have the opportunity to read a book for about 1 hour a week. Reading the work expressively, in a tone appropriate to the character and actions of the characters, making short stops at certain places of the work, and asking the child "What do you think will be the next development of the story" (it is necessary not to scold or rebuke during the conversation), as well as, after reading, it is advisable to organize a small conversation with the child about the events and events read [5].

"Carefully study the cover of the work" method. Another method recommended by foreign pedagogues is to carefully study the cover of the work. This method is used in the following order:

- 1) students are required to look at the cover of the work of art, pay attention to the main notes - the author's name, initials, and the name and illustration (decoration) of the work;
- 2) students examine the cover of the work;
- 3) students are invited to remember what information they have about the writer or poet who is the author of the work, his works;
- 4) students provide information about the author and his works;
- 5) a cartoon or feature film based on the work is watched under the guidance of the teacher;
- 6) students are given a task to compare the plot of the work and cartoons or feature films based on it;
- 7) under the guidance of the teacher, the performance of the task by the students is discussed [8].

"Verbal drawing" methodology. In the experience of foreign countries, not only methods, but also methods are based on effective methods in the formation of reading skills in children. One of such methods is the "Verbal painting" method. This method arises in the reader's mind during the process of reading an artistic work and serves to express the description of the images and plots in it [7]. This method is also known as "Word image". It is directed to the development of students' skills to clarify the images according to their specific characteristics with the help of words, according to which the student should not use words, adjectives, verbs that are not used in the process of reading the work to illuminate the images and plots [5].

"Literary Geniuses" game. The age and psychological characteristics of primary school students show that the use of game technologies is also effective in promoting reading among them. "Literary Geniuses" can be added to the list of artistic games. According to the rules of the game, the students are divided into two groups and during the specified time, they answer the questions about the literary works studied in the classroom and outside the classroom [3].

"Knowledge tree care" game. Russian pedagogue E.E. Moroz offers the game "Knowledge Tree Care" in order to awaken the love of reading and reading in students. It is suggested to use a poster during the game. The poster depicts a fairy tree. On separate leaves, the names of the fairy tales that the children read with their parents at home are written. Parents also take part in describing the "Fairy Tree". When students come to class, they stick a leaf with the names of the fairy tales they have read on the "Fairy Tree". After the start of the lesson, the children together with the teacher approach the classroom blackboard, show the leaves they hung on the "Fairy Tale Tree" and briefly describe the content of the fairy tale [8].

CONCLUSION

Pedagogical activities aimed at developing reading competencies in future English language teachers in foreign experiences are Kassil method, Ancient peoples" method, "Carefully studying the cover of the work" method, "Oral picture" method, "Literary geniuses" and "Knowledge tree care" is organized on the basis of game technologies. But taking into account the global changes, new socio-cultural needs, it is required to determine the well-founded principles of reading and reading skills formation in primary school students, as well as effective factors. In order to form interest in the examples of fiction in future English language teachers, formation of motivation for this activity in learners is of important pedagogical and psychological importance. As well as, while developing interest of the students in the examples of fiction literature, in cooperation with the school librarian and parents, it is required to stage selected excerpts from

various fairy tales, epics, examples of children's literature, and ensure their participation as much as possible.

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